

differential CP, the designed S-to-D block generates differential control signals and their symmetric wave forms are reinforced by the cross coupled inverters.

Fig. 4 Phase frequency detector with differential control output

Fig. 5 Proposed charge pump circuit

The CP circuit is ideally parallel connection of current source and current sink which are implemented by PMOS and NMOS. However, the output resistance of the sub-micron transistor is not large enough to be modeled as a current source and sink. Therefore, a current mismatch occurs due to the difference between the drain-source voltages of the PMOS and NMOS when dumping the charge to the LF. A cascode structure boosts output resistance by the gain of the common source amplifier. However the cascode structure reduces voltage headroom and legroom of the CP output so the structure is not popular under the sub-micron technology. Another dominant problem in designing the low noise CP is charge sharing. When the CP switches are open, the drain voltage of PMOS is pre-charged to VDD and drain voltage of NMOS is discharged to GND due to the parasitic capacitance of the transistor. When the switches are closed, the output capacitor charges are shared with pre-charged or discharged

parasitic capacitor which causes voltage ripple at every switching cycle.

Fig. 5 illustrates the designed CP circuit. The current sink is implemented with the cascode structure (MN1 and MN2).

Fig. 6 Simulated DC characteristics of the proposed charge pump

Fig. 7 Fabricated chip photo

The voltage legroom is secured by designing additional current source I_{CP} which is CP_OUT (output voltage) dependent (inversely proportional) current source. As the CP_OUT approaches to GND, more current is supplied to the CP then conduction current limitation caused by reduced legroom is compensated. The OP1 adjust gate voltage of MP1 with respect to the current of MN1. Also OP1 makes the node N1 the same with the CP_OUT , therefore the reference current is exactly mirrored to the core of the CP regardless of CP_OUT . In this way, current mismatch problem is minimized.

Differential architecture as shown in Fig. 5 guarantees constant current conduction to the CP core regardless of control signal. Constant current conduction mitigates charge sharing problems considerably, but the voltage difference between CP_OUT and $VREF$ still generates charge sharing. The inserted OP2 is designed to eliminate above mentioned problem by making the two nodes equal. The simulation results show that the current mismatch is bounded within 300 nA with 0.2 ~ 1.1 V output operating range.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The Fig. 7 is the die photograph of the fabricated design using TSMC 90 nm CMOS process. The reference frequency of the TCXO used in this paper is 50 MHz. The circuit draws the maximum 30 mW for PLL from a 1.2 V supply. The measured PLL frequencies, 18.2 ~ 23.2 GHz, which are translated into 54.6 ~ 69.4 GHz covers all 60-GHz band with enough margin.

Fig. 8 Measured frequency characteristics of the PLL

Fig. 9 Measured phase noise @ 20 GHz

The frequency range is measured by manipulating 8-bit integer programmable divider and 24-bit fractional SDM. Therefore the operation of the proposed pre-scalar is confirmed as far as 23.2 GHz. The measured tuning range is 25%. By using switchable fifteen capacitor arrays and four varactor arrays, the constant K_v is measured and well matched with simulation result (in Fig. 8). Due to the constant K_v , loop characteristics of all the resonance frequency is almost equal. The operational range of the CP is from 0.15 V to 1.09 V which is quiet well matched with simulation result. As a representative case, the phase noise of 20 GHz is selected and plotted in Fig. 9. A -58 dBc/Hz in-band noise and a -96.21 dBc/Hz noise at 1-MHz are measured. The measurement results shows that the proposed fraction PLL ensure 16 QAM data

communication in 60 GHz frequency.

V. CONCLUSION

A mm-wave fractional PLL frequency synthesizer was implemented in 90 nm CMOS process. The proposed VCO showed wide tuning range and constant K_v characteristics due to the combination of the capacitor and varactor arrays. The 20-GHz pre-scalar worked well as high as 23 GHz. The measured frequency and voltage tuning characteristics were well matched with simulation. The proposed circuit met the phase noise requirement of the 60 GHz system. Thus, the presented design can be a good PLL candidate for 60 GHz high speed wireless communication.

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